

Establishment of College Of Education, Policy Formulation, Planning and Implementation in Nigeria

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Abstract

This work examined the policy formulation, planning and implementation for the establishment of a college of Education. Literature reviewed was from the introduction. In view of the literature available, conclusions were drawn that the establishment of a college of Education means our society has gotten backbones. It also means possible development, qualitative teachers and better learning for students. That applicant that seek to establish a college of Education should do well to adhere strictly to the policies, planning etc. to achieve its implementation.

Keywords: Establishment, Policy, Formulation, Planning and Implementation.

INTRODUCTION

National Commission for colleges of Education Act 1989 and amended by Decree N012 of 1993 is responsible for the establishment of College of Education. The establishment of college of Education as a higher Education is indeed one of the backbones of our society. It is fundamental and necessary then that quality should be upheld because its quality will determine the quality of human resources and development.

Higher Education as we see it today is a complex system facilitating teaching, research and international cooperation (Mishra, 2017). In Nigeria, higher education is provided by universities, polytechnics/monotechnics, colleges of education, as well as institutes that prepare candidates for professional courses such as accounting, law, architecture, mass communication, etc.

It is a truism in education that the quality of education depends largely upon the quality of teachers. There is the likelihood that the students will not get quality education unless the teachers are qualitative.

According to stinnett (1962), Nelson, Polansky and Carlson (2000), whatever input is made in an educational system in respect of management, resources, facilities and array of instructional materials, will be little avail if the teacher is unskilled, poorly trained, or even ignorant. This explains why a college of Education should be established, to get the teachers and would be teachers trained and developed into professionalism and have a major aspect of national development which will cause a concretely laid down foundation to effect a purposeful development orientation.

That there are many specialties in teaching today, with their wide range of required skills and knowledge meant that teachers need to be well prepared to a degree for the vastly different nature of teaching functions, challenges and tasks therein. This point to the fact that for effectiveness and efficiency, teachers need to be given a professional education that will qualify them thus, as well as enable them to effectively perform the task of giving the appropriate support towards enhancing a virile and qualitative system of education in any nation. Prominent amongst the ways to achieve this, is the establishment of college of education. Proper Education of teachers is the foundation of quality in the educational system and this is the key to unlock all facts of development. Obviously, this is very relevant in nations that lookup to education as a vehicle for attaining the desired development in all sectors of national life.

According to Nwafor (2018) a College of Education is a college where the form of education which is planned and systematically tailored and applied for the cultivation of those who teach or will teach particularly but not exclusively, in primary and post primary levels of schooling is done. The concern of college of education worldwide is the training and preparing teachers and would be teachers for effective functioning at the school.

College of Education makes way for the professional training that teachers receive for them to be classified as professionals. According to Ipaye (1996) and FGN(2004), this is charged with the task of developing knowledge and skills as basis for practice, with preparing personnel entry into the teaching profession and with practicing professionals and encourage further the spirit of enquiry and creativity in teachers.

College of Education is therefore to function by equipping teachers with the wherewithal; both ethnical, intellectual competencies and skills, disposition, emotional and so forth, which will enable them, develop and imbue in their students the requisite educational and societal dispositions. The quality of any educational system therefore solely depends on the quality of teachers one finds in the school system.

Unfortunately, it is difficult to see a school these days that actually qualify for this requirement. This is because the trend of striving for quality has changed. It is an eye saw, that what occupies the mind now is paper qualification. In fact, the school system has decayed and decomposed when talking of quality. The teachers we have today in our school system have themselves involved in various forms of examination malpractice in their times in school. Then, where are we to see quality. Some of them parading with B.Sc., B.Ed. etc. certificates manipulate same from computer. In other words, these sets of teachers do not possess the qualification they claim they have. Some who have are virtually empty because they got it from the back door. They cannot defend such certificates because they were unable to attend classes being immersed in cult activities and other sinister engagements. It is not surprising today that many teachers we have in the school system cannot write and teach because of their background. Quality education cannot be achieved from a vacuum. Something must be done. Teachers are expected to show a difference as instructors in the school system. They should know that the society holds them to a very high esteem. The life of the school system partly rests upon their hands and they do not need to soil their image.

The school system cannot witness quality if the teacher themselves are not qualitative. They need to be trained to be able to teach well and satisfactory and to acquire discipline. The solution for this therefore, can best be proffered by the establishment of College of Education (Edet 2019).

This paper therefore tends to give an overview of the establishment of a college of education, policy formulation, planning and implementation.

Policy

According to Flippo (1980) a policy is a man- made rule of predetermined course of action that is established to guide the performance of work towards the organizational objectives. It is a standing plan that serves to guide people in execution of their tasks. They are statements of the organization's overall purposes and its objectives in the various areas with which its operations are concerned, Nwosu, (2015), defining policy said, policy serves as a road map for managers or school administrators in the school system. It refers to principles and rules of conduct which formulate, redefine, break into details and decide a number of actions that govern the relationship with employees in the attainment of the organization's objectives.

In view of the above, it means that policy formulation on the establishment of college of Education has to do with the plan of action, guidelines etc., to establish a college of Education. Hence this has to be put in place in other not to have or create anything that has to do with the establishment of College of Education from a vacuum, It is paramount that it has to be, to direct the way things have to be done, how things need to be done, what need to be done and where things need to be driven for proper placement.

Policy formulation

The policy or guidelines for the establishment of a college of Education in Nigeria takes the following order as provided by virtue of section 20A, National Minimum and Establishment of Institution Amendment Decree No.9 of 1993.

1. It may be sponsored or owned by the government of the Federal or of a State or Local Government or by any of the following bodies.
 - a. Company incorporated in Nigeria or
 - b. By an individual or association of individuals who are citizens of Nigeria and who satisfy the criteria set out in the schedule to this Act for establishment of Institutions.
2. An application for the establishment of the college of education shall be duly made to the Minister of Education through the National Commission for Colleges of Education.
3. No state, Local Government or College shall benefit from the education tax unless the application for the establishment of that College of Education was made in accordance with the provision of sub-section (1) of this section.
4. No person shall be granted approval to establish a College of Education unless the set standards or principles in the schedule to this Act have been satisfied.

Planning or principles for establishment of college of education

Generally speaking, planning has been defined by Kaufman (1997), as a process for determining where to go and identify the requirements for getting there in the most effective and efficient manner possible.

In the context of policy sciences, Dror 1963 defined planning as a set of decisions for action in the future, directed at achieving goals, by optimal means.

Idoli (2019) also has it that it is the prediction or projection of a set of decisions meant for the future in the present time and preparing to execute and implement same then. Planning is not what anybody will impulsively go into. It needs being careful and orderly. Meaning that the establishment of a college of education cannot be done in hurry or it will be missed out. Planning has to be put in place for safety and direction observation. More also, College of Education is the concern of educational system and so, anything and way planned to establish it, must take the laid down principles. Educational planning is not ordinary, it must pertain to education. The planning to establish college of education must be educational planning.

According to Anderson and Bowman (1967), educational planning is the process of preparing a set of decisions for future actions pertaining to education. The decision packaged to be executed in the future must concern or connect things of education. Combs (1974) amplifies it that educational planning in its broadest generic sense, is the application of rational systematic analysis to the process of educational development with the aim of making education more effective and efficient in responding to the needs and goals of its students and society.

Educational planning as a field of study may be modern but the act of deciding in advance, what you want to do and how you are going to do it is as old as the school system itself. This explains the fact that it is the responsibility of every school to decide before the beginning of the year, the number of students the school could take in the preceding year, classrooms, teachers and furniture needed.

In the views of Denga in Mbipom (2000) educational planning involves the formulation of educational policies and objectives, the co-ordination of various educational proposals, the projection of enrollments, compilation of school statistics, educational costing and budgeting, establishment of new schools and expansion of existing ones.

Contemporarily, educational planning is concerned with the social economic and man power development of the whole nation. It is naturally a complex process. It is on this note that the establishment of a college of education must be well planned and the following processes required and satisfied;

1. The academic structure and spread of discipline of the college of Education shall be such as would cater for areas of needs.
2. There shall be evidence produced to show that institution would be provided with adequate funding, both capital and recurrent and Academic and support staff. The proposal staffing guidelines shall meet with current guidelines for the National Commission for Colleges of Education
3. The Federal Government must be satisfied that on approval being given, the source of funding and necessary funds will be available.
4. The Federal Government or in its accredited agency shall ascertain and be satisfied itself that the fixed and enabling assets, that is funds, land, moveable and immovable assets are appropriate for establishing the college of Education in the light of such factors as: the type of college of Education envisaged, its philosophy and objectives and the cost of goods and services prevailing at the time. It must be that the assets shall be assigned to the college on approval being given for the college to be established and that the applicant was supplied a concrete and guaranteed source of financial support for the college of Education to the tune of ₦50 million over a period of 5 years.
5. A proposed college of Education shall have clearing spelt out master plan for the infrastructural and programme development for at least 20 to 25 years which shall make adequate provision for plan space, aesthetic beauty and fixed fiscal assets and minimal land area of 15 hectares in a salutary site. In spite of the above, the site distance from an urban complex shall take into account availability of municipal services, including water, transportation, private accommodation, communication and other consequential inadequate in its community.
6. A proposed college of Education shall have an adequate environment base and shall be open to all Nigerians irrespective of ethnic derivation, social status, religious or political persuasion. Accordingly, it shall be planned in such a way that its laws and status shall not conflict with the conventional responsibilities in academia or interfere with avowed traditional autonomy.
7. To pre-empt problems of inadequate municipal facilities, the establishment of a college of education shall be planned in such a way that the proposed college shall have a clear policy on student and staff accommodation and catering services.
8. The proposed college of education shall have a well-articulated mission and set of objectives which may be original and innovative but unequivocally in consonance with the socio-economic and political aspirations of Nigeria.
9. Planning shall be that, to create and sustain credibility and confidence from the start, the administrative structure of the proposed college of Education shall not depart too radically from established norms.
10. The library, laboratory and workshop facilities including instructional tools and consumables shall be adequate and there shall be long range plans for sustaining them.

11. The planning and feasibility report of the proposed college of Education include proposal contracts and affiliation with existing similar institutions and plans for cooperation and interaction.

IMPLEMENTATION

It has been established that no person shall be granted approval to establish a college of Education unless the principles or planning set out in the schedule to this Act have been satisfied.

What it means is that, if the applicant is not able to satisfy the principles or planning set out, approval is not given, the implementation is impossible. It should be properly noted that inconsistency and contradictory nature of the policies and practices and even instability in administration shall cause dwarfism in the well implementation of the establishment of a proposed college of Education. Therefore, an applicant for the establishment of a proposed college of education ought to adhere strictly to the planning principles, such as being able to:

1. Provide academic structure and discipline that will cater for the capital and recurrent expenditure.
2. Ensure that adequate fund is provided for the capital and recurrent expenditure.
3. Ensure the Federal Government is satisfied that the fixed assets are appropriate for establishing the college.
4. Ensure that the N50 million guarantee for 5years period is available
5. Ensure that there is available 25 hectares of land for the establishment of the college, and other planning principles necessary.

CONCLUSION

In the light of literature above, the following conclusions were drawn;

That the establishment of a college of Education means that our society has gotten backbones and this will ensure possible development and qualitative teachers and better learning for students.

That to establish a college of Education the applicant must strictly adhere to the policy or policies formulated and planning to succeed in the implementation.

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